

E-LaaS

Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

E-LaaS Workshops

August 20 - 21, 2024

Faculty of Transport, Warsaw University of Technology (Poland)

SUB-REPORT FOR WP6

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European
Commission

URBAN EUROPE

Project funding information

E-Laas project is carried out in an international consortium. Project coordinator in Europe: Chalmers University of Technology (Sweden), project coordinator in China: Shanghai University (China), consortium members: Tsinghua University (China), Warsaw University of Technology (Poland), cooperation partners: Stockholms stad, Trafikkontoret (Sweden), ParkUnload (Spain), Metropolis GZM (Poland), Shanghai Urban-Rural Construction and Transportation Department (China), Volvo Group Trucks Technology and Operations (Sweden).

- *The Chinese part of the project is funded by National Natural Science Foundation of China*

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Workshops objectives	4
3. Organization of Workshops	4
3.1. Program	4
3.2. Registration system:	5
3.3. Website	6
3.4. Informational materials	8
4. Workshops summary	9
4.1. Workshop opening.....	9
4.2. Networking session	10
4.3. Discussion panels	10
4.4. Technical session.....	19
4.5. Workshop summary	19
4.6. Photo report	20
5. Additional internal consortium meeting – August 22, 2024	21
6. Post-Workshop communications	21

1. Introduction

In accordance with the project's assumptions, the first Workshops were held in Poland on August 20-21. In addition, the workshops were accompanied by internal consortium meetings, which took place on August 20, 21, and 22. Many experts, NGOs, and local authorities were invited to participate in the workshops. In total, about 50 people attended the event. This report documents the organization and course of the workshops. To this end, the following were discussed:

- the objectives of the workshops,
- organization of the workshops, including the program, informational and promotional materials,
- summary of the workshops.

2. Workshops objectives

The E-Laas Workshops was hold on August 20 – 21, 2024, at the Faculty of Transport of the Warsaw University of Technology, Koszykowa 75, 00-662 Warsaw, Poland. The workshops were organized under the E-Laas (Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service) project. The aims of the workshops are to:

- Enable participants to share knowledge and experiences in the field of urban logistics and energy-efficient transport solutions.
- Identify critical areas of urban logistics activities and propose sustainable improvements from the perspectives of city and regional organizers, authorities, and society.
- Present the latest research and solutions supporting sustainable urban logistics.
- Build and strengthen professional networks among participants to create synergies and potential research and development collaborations.

Target Audience:

- Researchers specializing in transport logistics and process optimization.
- Industry representatives, entrepreneurs, NGOs operating in the logistics, transport, and modern technology sectors.
- Representatives of regional and urban authorities responsible for planning and managing urban transport infrastructure.
- Students and PhD candidates studying topics related to the workshop themes, seeking inspiration and professional development opportunities.

3. Organization of Workshops

3.1. Program

First Day – Tuesday (August 20, 2024)

- 10:00 – 11:00: Participant Registration
- 11:00 – 11:20: Workshop Opening
- 11:20 – 12:30: Networking: E-Laas, Urbfrail, Mobile Energy Storage
- 12:30 – 13:30: Lunch
- 13:30 – 15:00: Discussion Panel 1 (SULP)
- 15:00 – 15:30: Coffee Break
- 15:30 – 17:00: Discussion Panel 2 (Urban Logistics from the Operator's Perspective)
- 17:00 – 17:30: Day Summary

Second Day – Wednesday (August 21, 2024)

- 10:00 – 11:00: Participant Registration
- 11:00 – 12:30: Technical Session Part 1*
- 12:30 – 14:00: Lunch
- 14:00 – 15:30: Technical Session Part 2*
- 15:30 – 16:00: Workshop Summary and Closing

*Presentation of E-Laas Partners:

- 11:00 – 11:45: Warsaw University of Technology
- 11:45 – 12:30: Chalmers University of Technology
- 14:00 – 14:45: Shanghai University
- 14:45 – 15:30: Tsinghua University

3.2. Registration system:

The registration system was developed using MS Forms in Polish and English.

A screenshot of the registration form content. The form is titled "E-Laas Workshops August 20 - 21, 2024" and includes a "Required" section with the following fields:

- 1. First name *
- 2. Last name *
- 3. Affiliation/Company name *
- 4. E-mail address *

Below these fields is a confirmation section: "5. I confirm my participation on the following days *", with two radio button options: "August 20, 2024 - 11:00 - 17:30" and "August 21, 2024 - 11:00 - 16:00". To the right of the form, there is a "What data do we collect?" section listing "First name, last name, affiliation/company name, email address" and a "How do we use these data?" section listing "Confirmation, contact with participants". Below this is a "General Data Protection Regulation at Warsaw University of Technology (GDPR)" section with 11 numbered points. At the bottom right, there is a "Photography" section with a radio button for "I accept" and a "Submit" button. A Microsoft 365 privacy notice is visible at the very bottom.

3.3. Website

English version:

<https://www.wt.pw.edu.pl/Badania-i-nauka/Konferencje/Rok-2024/Warsztaty-E-Laas-E-Laas-Workshops/E-Laas-Workshops>

Polish version:

<https://www.wt.pw.edu.pl/Badania-i-nauka/Konferencje/Rok-2024/Warsztaty-E-Laas-E-Laas-Workshops/Warsztaty-E-Laas>

E-Laas Workshops

Opublikowano: 10.06.2024 13:34

Warsaw 20-21.08.2024

1. E-Laas Workshops
2. Agenda
3. Registration Form
4. Venue
5. About E-Laas
6. Contact

1. E-Laas Workshops

The E-Laas Workshops will be held on August 20 – 21, 2024, at the Faculty of Transport of the Warsaw University of Technology, Koszykowa 75, 00-662 Warsaw, Poland.

Workshop Objective:

The workshops are organized under the E-Laas (Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service) project. The aims of the workshops are to:

- Enable participants to share knowledge and experiences in the field of urban logistics and energy-efficient transport solutions.
- Identify critical areas of urban logistics activities and propose sustainable improvements from the perspectives of city and regional organizers, authorities, and society.
- Present the latest research and solutions supporting sustainable urban logistics.
- Build and strengthen professional networks among participants to create synergies and potential research and development collaborations.

Target Audience:

- Researchers specializing in transport logistics and process optimization.
- Industry representatives, entrepreneurs, NGOs operating in the logistics, transport, and modern technology sectors.
- Representatives of regional and urban authorities responsible for planning and managing urban transport infrastructure.
- Students and PhD candidates studying topics related to the workshop themes, seeking inspiration and professional development opportunities.

Why Attend:

- Gain insights into the latest research and innovations in energy-efficient urban logistics.
- Network with experts, researchers, and industry representatives, potentially leading to future scientific collaborations.
- Exchange experiences and best practices in managing urban logistics processes, considering the energy consumption of the transport system.
- Participate in discussion panels to influence the assumptions and directions of research within the E-Laas project and the broader industry development.
- Draw inspiration for further research in new areas related to urban logistics and transport activities.
- Obtain ideas and solutions that can be implemented in your professional or research work.
- Enhance your qualifications and acquire new knowledge on the latest logistics solutions.

Important Information:

- Participation in the workshops is free, but prior registration is required (by August 1).
- Organizers provide lunch and coffee breaks.
- Organizers do not offer accommodation.
- Participation will be confirmed with a certificate.
- The number of participants is limited to 100 – early registration is recommended.
- The event will be conducted in English.

2. Agenda

The E-Laas Workshops are divided into three main sessions (networking, discussion panels, technical session).

1. Networking Session

This crucial event element aims to maximize the benefits of the workshops, support collaboration among participants, and accelerate progress in sustainable urban logistics. Three research projects will be presented during this session:

- E-Laas (Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service)
- Urbfrail (Revitalization of Inner-Urban Freight Rail Hubs)
- The concept of creating a special vehicle as a mobile electric energy storage unit, including guidelines for design and software development for synergy of renewable energy sources and consumers within the urban energy process.

Presenting these projects with different goals but interconnected from the perspective of logistics and energy management will identify areas where the projects can complement and support each other, leading to better resource utilization and more efficient, innovative solutions. Understanding these projects will give participants a broader perspective on urban logistics and energy management challenges and opportunities, enhancing the planning and implementation of their activities.

2. Discussion Panels

Two discussion panels will be held during the workshops:

- DP1: Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans (SULP)
- DP2: Urban Logistics from the Perspective of Logistics Operators

The discussion panels are essential for understanding and addressing urban logistics challenges from various perspectives: logistics operators, city managers, customers, and society. Discussions will identify barriers to the development of logistics systems, such as fleet management, delivery organization, and energy consumption optimization, and understand infrastructural and regulatory challenges. Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans (SULP) strategies supporting emission reduction and congestion alleviation, thereby improving urban living quality, will be discussed. The panels will also focus on energy transformation, including transport electrification and the development of alternative delivery systems such as parcel lockers, drones, and cargo bikes. These discussions will foster the exchange of experiences, best practices, and the integration of activities from various stakeholders, leading to more coordinated and innovative solutions in urban logistics.

3. Technical Session

The technical session will be an opportunity to present advanced research conducted by teams from Warsaw University of Technology, Chalmers University, Shanghai University, and Tsinghua University. The teams will focus on presenting research in urban logistics process management, parking infrastructure management, and electric vehicle charging or large-scale system modelling, optimization, and simulation. This session will allow participants to learn about innovative solutions and technologies, contributing to new research areas and potential collaboration opportunities in transport.

Provisional Workshop Program:

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- 11:00 – 11:20: Workshop Opening
- 11:20 – 12:30: Networking: E-Laas, Urbfrail, Mobile Energy Storage
- 12:30 – 13:30: Lunch
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- 15:00 – 15:30: Coffee Break
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- 17:00 – 17:30: Day Summary

Second Day – Wednesday (August 21, 2024)

- 10:00 – 11:00: Participant Registration
- 11:00 – 12:30: Technical Session Part 1*
- 12:30 – 14:00: Lunch
- 14:00 – 15:30: Technical Session Part 2*
- 15:30 – 16:00: Workshop Summary and Closing

*Presentation of E-Laas Partners:

- 11:00 – 11:45: Warsaw University of Technology
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- 14:00 – 14:45: Shanghai University
- 14:45 – 15:30: Tsinghua University

Detailed Program:

The detailed program will be published soon. Please regularly check our website.

3. Registration Form

We invite you to register for the E-Laas workshops. Please complete the registration form by August 1, 2024. Due to the limited number of places, we encourage early registration to secure participation in the event. Please fill in all required fields in the form to help us prepare for your participation. If you have any questions regarding registration, please contact the organizers (contact information is available in the "Contact" section). Participation in the workshops is free. The organizers provide lunch and coffee breaks. Participation will be confirmed with a certificate.

The registration form is available in both Polish and English:

<https://forms.office.com/e/2WSmjQVcFg>

4. Venue

The E-Laas Workshops will take place at the **Faculty of Transport of the Warsaw University of Technology, Koszykowa 75, 00-662 Warsaw.**

The main events will be held in the **Auditorium of the Faculty in the New Wing of the Faculty of Transport,**

**level -1,
Auditorium S055.**

Google Map:

<https://maps.app.goo.gl/6xS34MdNoz4DNrp7>

What we are going to do:

- > Develop energy-efficient urban logistics solutions with quantitative energy consumption characteristics, allowing precise resource management and minimisation of losses.
- > Develop intelligent, multimodal, and energy-efficient micro-delivery systems, utilising various modes of transport and optimised delivery routes, contributing to reduced energy consumption.
- > Analyse disturbances in urban logistics tasks and propose reconfigurable solutions to regain energy efficiency. This key project element allows adaptation to changing conditions and constraints in urban freight transport.
- > Develop concepts for co-organising distribution services and unloading zones through charging station infrastructure and the energy network, considering intelligent charging rules and the impact of energy prices on delivery costs. This is an innovative approach to energy management in urban logistics.
- > Quantify urban freight transport demand and analyse customer behaviour. These analyses enable more precise delivery planning and energy consumption minimisation.
- > Analyse digital and physical components along with the holistic concept of logistics as a service. This approach considers the entire logistics process, allowing comprehensive energy management.
- > Develop concepts for scalable, multimodal, and energy-efficient distribution systems, enabling efficient adaptation of urban logistics to various conditions, areas, and requirements.
- > Develop new ways to increase social responsibility through E-Laas. This project aims not only to save energy but also to create more sustainable and environmentally friendly logistics solutions.

Consortium:

The project is implemented by an international consortium. Project coordinator in Europe: Chalmers University of Technology (Sweden), project coordinator in China: Shanghai University (China), consortium members: Tsinghua University (China), Warsaw University of Technology (Poland), cooperating partners: Stockholms stad Trafikkontoret (Sweden), ParkUnload (Spain), Metropolia GZM (Poland), Shanghai Urban-Rural Construction and Transportation Department (China), Volvo Group Trucks Technology and Operations (Sweden).

Project Funding:

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- > The Polish part of the project is funded by the National Science Center (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134).
- > The Chinese part of the project is funded by the National Natural Science Foundation of China.
- > The Swedish part of the project is funded by the Swedish Energy Agency.

Additional Information:

Public Transport Access: The event location provides convenient access by public transport, with numerous tram, bus, and metro stops nearby:

- > Metro Politechnika Station (5 minutes walk)
- > Tram and bus stops (Plac Politechniki, Nowowiejska, Koszykowa)
- > Warsaw Central Station (10 minutes walk)

Parking: Parking will be available for participants on the campus grounds. The number of parking spaces is limited. To reserve a parking, please contact the organizer.

5. About E-Laas

Project Objective:

The E-Laas project aims to create an innovative platform that minimises energy consumption in the distribution process from consolidation centres to customer doors. This platform facilitates energy savings at every distribution stage.

6. Contact

For any questions regarding the E-Laas workshops, please contact us. We are at your disposal and will gladly provide any information.

Event Coordinator:

Emilian Szczepański

Email: emilian.szczepanski@pw.edu.pl

Phone: +48 22 234 14 10

Event Organizers:

Mariusz Izdebski

Marianna Jacyna

Roland Jachimowski

Michał Kłodawski

Konrad Lewczuk

Jakub Murawski

Jan Paszkowski

Rating: 0/5 (0 votes cast)

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ul. Koszykowa 75, 00-662 Warszawa

3.4. Informational materials

The informational materials were prepared in English. They include a leaflet, roll-up banner, certificate of participation, and participant ID:

- Leaflet:

- Roll-up:

- certificate of participation

- participant ID

4. Workshops summary

4.1. Workshop opening

The workshops were opened by Prof. Marianna Jacyna, Dean of the Faculty of Transport at the Warsaw University of Technology, who welcomed the participants and guests. In her speech, she emphasized the importance of urban logistics in the face of increasing urbanization, growing demand for transport, and challenges related to energy consumption and environmental pollution. She highlighted the need to develop innovative solutions to ensure

sustainable urban development and improve the quality of life for city residents. She wished the participants fruitful deliberations and inspiring discussions.

4.2. Networking session

The networking session provided an opportunity to present ongoing research projects and exchange experiences. Three key projects were presented during this session:

1. E-Laas (Energy Optimal Urban Logistics As A Service) - Emilian Szczepański discussed an innovative approach to shaping urban logistics that takes into account social aspects and energy management in multimodal last-mile delivery systems.
2. UrbFRail (Revitalization of Inner-Urban Freight Rail Hubs) - Maciej Śmieszek presented a tool supporting cities in developing urban freight zones by rail, addressing key challenges and success factors for adapting urban rail spurs for distribution purposes.
3. Integration of Mobile Electricity Storage Facilities with Renewable Energy Sources in Urban Transport Hubs - Krzysztof Zagrajek presented the concept of a mobile electricity storage facility that supports the integration of renewable energy sources in urban transport hubs.

4.3. Discussion panels

The discussion panels, moderated by Prof. Konrad Lewczuk from the Warsaw University of Technology, were a key element of the workshops, enabling a deeper understanding of urban logistics challenges and future directions. The panels brought together distinguished experts from various fields who shared their knowledge and experiences.

– Panel on Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans (SULP)

The panel featured Mirosław Czerliński from the Warsaw University of Technology, Bartłomiej Wiertel from Via Vistula, and Aleksander Sobota from the Upper Silesian-Zagłębie Metropolis. The discussion focused on the importance of Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans (SULP) as a key tool for planning sustainable urban logistics. Experts discussed the challenges of their implementation, such as integrating logistics with urban spatial planning, engaging various stakeholders, and using modern technologies and analytical tools to optimize logistics processes. Panelists emphasized that SULPs are essential for creating more efficient and sustainable logistics systems that can help reduce emissions and improve the quality of life for city residents. The discussion highlighted the need to develop flexible plans that account for the diverse needs of cities and local communities.

Surveys conducted among participants during the panel:

1. Which area is most important in sustainable urban logistics plans?

20 Odpowiedzi

● Integrated spatial planning	5
● Optimization of urban freight transport	8
● Reduction of CO2 and PM emissions	5
● Integration with the urban energy policy	2
● Inne	0

2. Do you think SULP should be integrated or include:

20 Odpowiedzi

● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Neutral ● Agree ● Strongly agree

urban energy management strategy
 spatial development strategy of the city
 climate change adaptation strategy

3. Please rank the following challenges according to their importance in creating a SULP:

20 Odpowiedzi

Pozycja Opcje

1	Problems with integrating different sectors and stakeholders
2	Lack of coherence in local and national policies
3	Lack of funding and resources
4	Low public awareness and resistance from residents
5	Complexity in modelling and forecasting the effects

4. Who should have primary responsibility for urban sustainability?

20 Odpowiedzi

● Government	4
● Local authorities	5
● Logistics companies	0
● Local community	0
● All of the above in equal	11

5. What are the most common constraints that cargo suppliers face in urban areas?

20 Odpowiedzi

● Legal restrictions (e.g. entry bans, clean air zones)	6
● Technical problems (e.g. lack of access to infrastructure, lack of IT tools)	7
● Architectural barriers (e.g. narrow streets, lack of unloading spots)	16
● Operational restrictions (e.g. time windows)	4
● Inne	0

6. Do you think cargo suppliers often have to break the law to make city deliveries?

20 Odpowiedzi

● Yes, it is inevitable and very common	7
● Yes, but it can be minimized	9
● No, current solutions allow compliance with regulations	1
● No, any violations are due to the habits of suppliers	2
● I have no opinion	1

7. What solutions could alleviate the problems faced by cargo suppliers in high-traffic urban areas?

20 Odpowiedzi

● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Neutral ● Agree ● Strongly agree

8. Are the current regulations governing deliveries in cities sufficient?

20 Odpowiedzi

- Yes, they are sufficient 1
- Yes, but requires minor adjustments 4
- No, they are too restrictive 0
- No, they are insufficient 13
- I have no opinion 2

9. Which modern urban delivery models do you consider to be the most promising and likely to increase delivery efficiency?

20 Odpowiedzi

● 1 - No potential ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 - High potential

10. What are the best practices for implementing modern urban delivery models that are worth considering?

20 Odpowiedzi

- Public-private cooperation 11
- Enterprise cooperation 7
- Shared logistics infrastructure 12
- Traffic monitoring and access to real-time data 7
- Development of dedicated transport infrastructure by the city 14
- Stimulating ecological delivery systems by implementing privileges for selected means of... 4
- Inne 0

11. Please rank the following technological innovations that will have the greatest impact on the future of urban transport and logistics in the coming years?

20 Odpowiedzi

12. To what extent do you think educating children, young people, and citizens about urban logistics is crucial to improving its effectiveness?

20 Odpowiedzi

Popierające	9
Pasywne	4
Krytyczne	7

– Panel on Urban Logistics from the Operator’s Perspective

This panel featured Mirosław Gral from Last Mile Experts, Daniel Trzaskowski from Carefleet S.A., and Michał Wojtal from Pointpack S.A. The discussion focused on challenges related to managing urban logistics from the operators’ perspective. Topics included fleet management, integration of electric vehicles, last-mile delivery optimization, and the importance of cooperation between operators to increase operational efficiency. Experts agreed that the future of urban logistics will depend on operators' ability to adapt to new technologies and changing customer needs. Attention was drawn to the need for developing digital platforms that can support better resource management and coordination among different stakeholders, which, in the long term, will reduce operating costs and increase delivery efficiency.

Surveys conducted among participants during the panel:

1. Which vehicle ownership model do you consider the most effective from the perspective of a logistics operator operating in the city?

20 Odpowiedzi

● Vehicle Ownership by Operator	5
● Vehicle Ownership by Couriers	6
● Vehicle Leasing	5
● Short-Term Rental	1
● Long-Term Rental	1
● Fleet Sharing (Car Sharing)	2

2. Please rank the following challenges related to courier fleet management by their importance:

18 Odpowiedzi

Pozycja Opcje

1	Vehicle purchase and maintenance costs
2	Route and operation optimization Integrating electric vehicles into the fleet
3	Monitoring and evaluating courier performance
4	Vehicle maintenance and servicing
5	Meeting legal regulations

Pierwszy wybór Ostatni wybór

3. What are the biggest challenges facing couriers working in cities?

20 Odpowiedzi

● Traffic jams and restrictions	13
● Parking problems	16
● High operating costs	6
● Customer requirements for fast deliveries	10
● Time windows	5
● Inne	1

4. To what extent do you think that:

20 Odpowiedzi

- No, definitely
- No, it is of marginal importance
- Neutral
- Yes, but to a limited extent
- Yes, definitely

sustainable logistics solutions (e.g. electric vehicles, bicycle deliveries) are necessary in city logistics

personal deliveries (e.g. by private individuals) will grow in importance in city logistics

integration of suppliers', manufacturers' and operators' systems is necessary for effective city logistics management

5. What are the biggest obstacles to integrating the systems of various supply chain participants (suppliers, producers, recipients) in city logistics?

20 Odpowiedzi

- Lack of technological standards 7
- Data security issues 12
- Low interoperability of systems 9
- Lack of willingness to cooperate 14
- High competition 9
- Inne 1

6. How can platforms integrating logistics operators reduce operating costs and improve efficiency?

20 Odpowiedzi

- Increased transparency of operations 4
- Better management and monitoring of resources 10
- Reduced empty runs 13
- Facilitated cooperation between operators 11
- Inne 1

7. Please rank the following factors according to their impact on encouraging operators to cooperate in last-mile deliveries

19 Odpowiedzi

8. What technological innovations or other actions, such as legal measures, could impact the future of urban transport and logistics from an operator's perspective?

20 Odpowiedzi

- Development of autonomous and intelligent technologies 17
- Changes in regulations on urban logistics 7
- Investments in electric vehicle charging infrastructure 5
- Introduction of SULP in cities 8
- Inne 0

9. How will implementing SULP (Sustainable Urban Logistics Plan) in a given city affect logistics from the operator's perspective?

19 Odpowiedzi

- It will improve logistics efficiency 8
- It will cause a decrease in logistics efficiency 7
- It will complicate the delivery process 8
- It will increase the costs of operators 4
- It will increase the energy demand 2
- It will not affect logistics efficiency 3

4.4. Technical session

During the technical session, advanced research conducted by various academic teams was presented:

- Presentations from the Warsaw University of Technology (WUT): Emilian Szczepański presented current research results within the E-Laas project, focusing on energy management in urban logistics and stakeholder surveys in logistics systems. Jan Paszkowski discussed the use of macro-simulations for modeling urban freight transport for urban logistics needs. Konrad Lewczuk presented the use of the Flexsim tool for micro-simulation of last-mile delivery systems.
- Presentations from Chalmers University of Technology (CUT): Balazs Kulcsar and Fangting Zhou presented collaboration opportunities with Chalmers University of Technology and research on transport services in the "as a Service" model and intelligent energy pricing policies.
- Presentations from Shanghai University (SU): Jingwen Wu presented the courier routing problem in a new last-mile logistics service, based on stochastic modeling that accounts for the uncertainty of future orders. Xueting He presented route modeling for customized on-demand bus services, developing a new variant of the vehicle routing problem.
- Presentations from Tsinghua University (TU): Kai Wang presented research on route planning and passenger mobility systems using drones, as well as cargo transportation with drones and courier vehicles as drone hubs.

4.5. Workshop summary

The E-Laas Workshops concluded successfully, receiving enthusiastic feedback from participants. Over the two-day event, many key issues related to sustainable urban logistics were discussed, and several important conclusions were highlighted that could significantly impact the future development of this field.

The importance of urban logistics in the context of global challenges: urban logistics plays an increasingly important role in the sustainable development of cities worldwide. In the face of growing urbanization, cities are becoming centers not only of social life but also of intense economic activity, leading to increased demand for efficient and eco-friendly logistics solutions. Workshop participants emphasized that urbanization challenges require innovative logistics planning approaches that address both residents' needs and the need for environmental protection.

The impact of logistics on the quality of life in cities: efficient urban logistics directly impacts the quality of life of residents. Proper delivery management, minimizing road congestion, and reducing emissions are crucial for improving urban living conditions and the health of residents. During the discussion panels, it was indicated that one of the priorities is the implementation of logistics systems that effectively balance economic needs with environmental requirements.

The role of new technologies: the workshops emphasized that technological progress opens new possibilities in urban logistics. Modern technologies, such as drones, delivery robots, electric vehicles, and mobile logistics hubs, enable the creation of more efficient, faster, and eco-friendly delivery systems. In particular, attention was drawn to the importance of integrating advanced planning and analytical tools that allow better alignment of logistics services with the needs of residents and businesses.

The importance of collaboration and integration: workshop participants agreed that cooperation between different stakeholders—local authorities, logistics operators, businesses, and residents—is crucial for achieving sustainable urban logistics development. Integrated approaches and joint actions can lead to solutions that are not only efficient but also sustainable and socially responsible.

The need for developing sustainable urban logistics plans (SULP): the growing importance of Sustainable Urban Logistics Plans was emphasized as a tool that enables cities to plan logistics in a way that minimizes negative environmental impacts while meeting economic and social needs. SULPs help cities better prepare for future challenges, such as climate change, increasing population density, and growing demand for transport services.

The E-Laas Workshops created a unique platform for knowledge and experience exchange, which will contribute to the further development of sustainable urban logistics and the implementation of innovative transport solutions. Organizers and participants expressed hope that the acquired knowledge and established connections will result in new initiatives and collaborations in urban logistics.

4.6. Photo report

5. Additional internal consortium meeting – August 22, 2024

- Discussion on project progress,
- Discussion of next steps in the project,
- Discussion of potential in further joint research work,
- Discussion of next E-Laas workshops (China),
- Discussion on deepening cooperation and meeting with the Vice-Rector of WUT, Prof. Mariusz Malinowski

6. Post-Workshop communications

- Faculty of Transport WUT website::

- English:

<https://www.wt.pw.edu.pl/Badania-i-nauka/Konferencje/Rok-2024/Warsztaty-E-Laas-E-Laas-Workshops/Workshops-summary>

- Polish:
<https://www.wt.pw.edu.pl/Badania-i-nauka/Konferencje/Rok-2024/Warsztaty-E-Laas-E-Laas-Workshops/Relacja-z-warsztatow>
- Industry portal:
<https://intermodalnews.pl/2024/08/30/zrownowazona-logistyka-miejska-na-warsztatach-e-laas/>
- LinkedIn:
 - by Mirosław Grał:
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/mirek-gral-lme_e-laas-workshops-activity-7229391611661541380-plk4?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
 - by Carefleet:
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/carefleet-sa_carefleet-elektromobilnoagjafd-najem-activity-7232658407609032705-JpIS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop